

RISK DISCLOSURE ANALYSIS OF INDONESIAN BANKING BASED ON PILLAR 3 OF BASSEL II

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Abstract

Banking is an institution that functions as a place for financial management or financial intermediary (financial intermediary) between parties who have funds and those who manage these funds. Banking has a very important role in the collection or collection of funds and also the distribution of funds in the real sector which functions as a framework for economic growth. The results of this study indicate that risk disclosure is very important to be carried out in banking institutions. This is because banking institutions are very vulnerable to risk, with disclosure of the risks that will be faced by banking institutions in Indonesia in the future a management can be carried out on these risks in minimizing the adverse effects caused by these risks. Risk management provides a systematic and structured view in solving problems that may arise in the future. The application of this risk management in the banking world with the Basel II conversion is expected to make banks healthier so that the financial condition of a country will be better.

Keywords: Basel II, Risk Disclosure, Indonesian Banking

JEL Classification Codes: E51, G24

1. INTRODUCTION

Banking is an institution that functions as a place for financial management or financial intermediary (financial intermediary) between parties who have funds and those who manage these funds. Banking has a very important role in the collection or collection of funds and also the distribution of funds in the real sector which functions as a framework for economic growth. In addition, banks are institutions that play a role in providing or providing services in the financial sector.

On this basis, banking is one of the institutions that have an important role in the financial sector and also in economic growth (Glinting et al., 2020). So every bank in Indonesia is required to avoid the risks that affect the bank. Banking is known as an institution that has the greatest risk in its operational process. In the process of carrying out their operational activities, banks are more vulnerable to the risks they face compared to institutions or manufacturing companies. In addition to being vulnerable to risk, banks also have a fairly high level of regulation where regulations on banking have been regulated in Bank Indonesia regulations.

In Indonesia itself, problems with banking risk have often occurred; this is because the process of implementing banking practices is not carried out in a healthy manner caused by

several factors in it. There is a lot of clear evidence of the banking risk problems that have occurred, for example about bad credit which causes the liquidation value of a bank to decrease (Ritonga et al., 2020). This is due to the lack of handling of the risks that occur. Another risk that has occurred is the existence of double reporting on financial performance, where this is due to the reluctance of banks to report how much profit the bank gets in a period of 1 (one) year.

From this explanation, it can be said that the banking sector must be able to be in a healthy condition in its operational processes and activities. Therefore, every bank in Indonesia must be able to know the risks faced in the operational process of its activities. Risk is a form of uncertainty, in a company or institution risk cannot be completely eliminated. In general, risk can be interpreted as a condition that is not certain to occur, but if it occurs it can have a good or bad impact. Likewise with banking in Indonesia where this risk cannot be eliminated, but the risk can be minimized (Tambunan et al., 2018).

Therefore, the risk disclosure score in banking institutions in Indonesia is very important. Disclosure of risk (risk disclosures score) is information provided by managers of banking institutions / banking management which is contained in financial reports every year and given to stakeholders for convenience in the decision-making process.

Disclosure of risk (risk disclosures score) carried out by financial institutions is a first step and is also appropriate to do. This is due to minimize the negative impact of the risks faced by banking institutions in Indonesia. Disclosure of risk (risk disclosures score) can be done in risk management, by disclosing risk will make it easier for managers in banking in Indonesia and make management better, this is because they have anticipated the factors that will be faced in the future.

In practice, Bank Indonesia has implemented a process for risk management for banking institutions, namely Basel II. Banking in Indonesia in operational practice is based on regulations and policies that have been adopted by banks around the world, namely the Basel Accord as a benchmark for banking health and banking vigilance.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Basel Accord is a banking regulation put forward by the Basel Committee on Bank Supervision (BCBS). The rules contained in the Basel Accord are contained in Basel II which provides recommendations on banking regulations regarding capital risk, market risk and operational risk. The objective of Basel is to ensure that banking institutions have sufficient capital value to meet all the obligations of banking institutions to their employees.

In the Basel Accord, it discusses how to identify sensitive risks in relation to capital, provides a broader and comprehensive coverage of all possible risks that arise and also discusses how to apply a more flexible approach to risk management in banking, and it is hoped that the principles of Basel This Accord II can be applied in all banks in the world.

In Basel II itself there are 3 main pillars that are used as regulations for the running of banking practices in Indonesia. The 3 pillars are minimum capital, supervision review and information disclosure. Banking practices in Indonesia are in progress in accordance with the 3 pillars of the regulation and most importantly, the practice of disclosing information, especially risk disclosure in Indonesian banking.

Several studies that have been conducted on banking in Indonesia are based on Basel II (Sambodo et al., 2020) said that risk mitigation in banks can be carried out based on the pillars contained in Basel II. Other research conducted by (Simamora, 2021) With the implementation in accordance with Basel II regulations, it is possible to identify the risks that will be faced. Other research conducted by (Yanti, 2020) there is knowing the effect of risk on credit, where the analysis process is carried out in accordance with the regulations in Basel II. And other research conducted by (Rahmawati & Purwanto, 2019) the influence of capital adequacy in accordance with the pillars in Basel II has an influence and role in risk taking in the Bank

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Research Framework

The research framework is a set of activities, procedures or stages carried out in conducting a research. The research framework is made so that this research is more conceptual and directed so that it is in accordance with the research objectives. At this stage it will be explained about the stages of research that must be carried out in order to facilitate the resolution of existing problems, as well as collect data related to research to obtain the data and information needed.

Image 1. Research Framework

3.2 Research Method

This research is a literature study conducted using qualitative methods, where the research is conducted by describing and describing the risks faced by banks based on Basel II. The technique of collecting data is by studying literature from various sources such as books, the internet and research journals that have the same topic as the researcher discussed.

3.3 Risk Management

There are many definitions of risk (risk). According to Ricky W. Griffin and Ronald J. Ebert, risk is uncertainty about future events. While Joel G. Siegel and Jae K. Shim define risk in three terms, the first is a situation that leads to a specific set of outcomes, where the results can be obtained with the probability that the decision maker knows. Second, is the variation in profits, sales, or other financial variables, and third is the possibility of a financial problem that affects the company's operating performance or financial position, such as economic risk, political uncertainty, and industry problems.

Risk management is an important element whose implementation really needs to be considered, especially at the Bank as a financial institution. The development of an effective framework, structure and tools to monitor risk using an Enterprise Risk Management (ERM) approach was started in 2007. During 2007, major work was completed in identifying risk events and planning scenarios to increase the effectiveness of the Bank in its ability to respond to potential or potential risks. Occurrence of risk events.

Risk management is defined as a logical and systematic method of identifying, quantifying, determining attitudes, determining solutions and monitoring and reporting risks that take place in each activity or process. Risk management is required to:

- a. Support the achievement of goals
- b. It is possible to engage in activities that provide a much higher chance of taking a higher risk; a higher risk is taken with the support of an appropriate attitude and solution to the risk.
- c. Reduces the chance of fatal errors.
- d. Realizing that risk can occur in every activity and action within the organization so that each individual must take and manage their own risk in accordance with their respective authorities and responsibilities.

3.4 Risk Disclosure

Risk disclosure is important because it helps stakeholders in obtaining the information needed to understand the risk profile and how management manages risk. Risk disclosure is also useful for monitoring risk and detecting potential problems so that early action can be taken so that these problems do not occur. Risk information is also useful for investors because it

can help determine a company's risk profile, reduce information asymmetry, estimate market values, and determine portfolio investment decisions.

Management is required to disclose a brief description of corporate governance which includes an explanation of the risks faced by the company and the efforts that have been made to manage these risks, for example: risks caused by fluctuations in exchange rates or interest rates, business competition, supply of raw materials, provisions of other countries or international regulations, and government policies.

3.5 Basel II

Risk management in the banking world is a major issue that is often discussed in terms of financial stability. Banking risk management was often discussed when Asia experienced the financial crisis, namely around 1997-1998. Risk Management in banking is standardized from the Basel Accord (an agreement of the world's central banks approved in the city of Basel), in this Basel Accord we discuss how to identify sensitive risks in relation to capital, providing a broader and comprehensive coverage. About all possible risks that arise and also discusses how to approach a more flexible approach in implementing this risk management in banking, and hopefully the principles of the Basel Accord II this can be applied in all banks in the world.

The implementation of risk management in banking will begin in 2006 (Basel Accord II) and at this time banks are competing to train the application of risk management in their daily operations. Adapting risk management in banking activities requires considerable effort, especially in improving performance in daily operational activities. The risk management for banking includes:

1. Implementation of financial regulations and supervisory authorization
2. More significant legal/legal aspects
3. Identifying international supervisory relationships among banking supervisory institutions.

Matters discussed in the Basel Accord II include:

1. Every policy made must pay attention to legal aspects, applicable market rules, accounting standards, human resources and organizational structure.
2. When making a policy, the bank must first look at the scale of the decision taken and must consider things such as applicable international rules, as well as the right time and way to implement the decision.
3. The banking supervisory agency must also conduct an assessment of the capabilities of each bank.
4. Before supervision is carried out, the bank concerned must have prepared everything (preparedness supervisory stage).
5. Finally, each bank is also required to make the necessary adjustments according to its domestic conditions (especially in the field of law).

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the research conducted related to risk disclosure with Basel II, the main goal of Basel II is so that all financial institutions or banks have a good portfolio, especially on crucial matters in financial institutions. In this case, it is necessary to disclose the risks faced by financial institutions. In financial institutions based on Basel II, in this case all financial institutions in the policy-making process and also the implementation of policies must be based on legal aspects, applicable regulations and also available resources. In the policy-making process, financial institutions are required to be able to observe all forms of policy in advance and also consider aspects such as regulations that apply on an international scale.

Banking is the institution that is closest to risk, especially with regard to money. The bank's position as a mediator has placed it as the most risky party in terms of risk. The fluctuating domestic, regional and international economic conditions also contribute to the formation of banking risk.¹³ In general; the risks that may be faced by banks include credit/financing risk, market risk, and liquidity risk. Liquidity risk), operational risk, legal risk, reputation risk, strategic risk, compliance risk, and so on. These various types of risks can be divided into two major groups, namely (1) systemic risk (systemic risk), namely the risk caused by certain macro conditions or situations, such as changes in the political situation, changes in government economic policies, changes in market situations, crisis or recession situations, and so on that have an impact on general economic conditions; and (2) un systemic risk, which is a unique risk, which is inherent in a particular company or business only.[5]

1. Financing Risk

Financing risk is the risk due to the failure of the customer or other party to fulfill obligations to the bank in accordance with the agreed agreement. This financing risk is one of the main risks in providing bank financing. Financing risk arises if the bank is unable to recover the principal installments and/or profit sharing/margin fees from the loans it provides or the investments it is making. The main cause of this financing risk is that it is too easy for banks to provide loans or make investments because they are too required to take advantage of excess liquidity, so that financing assessments are not accurate in anticipating various possible business risks they finance.

This risk will be more visible when the economy is hit by a crisis or recession. The decline in sales resulted in reduced company income, so the company had difficulty fulfilling its obligations to pay its debts. When the bank is about to execute its bad debt, the bank does not get adequate results, because the existing guarantees are not commensurate with the amount of financing it provides. In the end, the bank will experience severe liquidity difficulties, especially when it has a fairly large non-performing financing. This risk can be reduced by limiting the authority of financing decisions for each apparatus in charge of financing, based on their capabilities (authorize limit) and the limit on the amount (ceiling) of financing that can be given to certain businesses or companies (financing line limit).

2. Market Risk

Market risk is the loss that occurs to the portfolio owned by banks due to changes in market variables such as interest rates and exchange rates. However, many banks do not recognize interest rate risk, so banks do not experience interest rate-related risks.

Banks only need to manage market risk related to changes in exchange rates to reduce losses. This market risk includes 4 things, namely interest rate risk, foreign exchange risk, price risk, and liquidity risk. Foreign exchange risk arises when a bank takes an open position. This foreign exchange rate risk can be reduced by limiting or minimizing the position, or can even be avoided altogether if the bank always takes a square position. Included in the market risk section:

a. Benchmark Rate Risk

Benchmark rate risk is the risk due to changes in the price of financial instruments from trading book positions caused by changes in securities.

b. Exchange Rate Risk

Exchange rate risk is the risk due to changes in the value of trading book and banking book positions caused by changes in foreign exchange rates

c. Commodity Risk

Commodity risk is the risk due to changes in the price of financial instruments from trading book and banking book positions caused by changes in commodity prices.

d. Equity Risk

Equity risk is the risk due to changes in the price of financial instruments from the trading book position caused by changes in stock prices.

3. Liquidity Risk

The thing that causes bankruptcies, big or small, is not due to losses, but the inability to meet the bank's liquidity needs. Liquidity can be defined as the ability to provide cash flow quickly and at an equal cost. Liquidity is very important for banks to carry out their business operational transaction activities, meet urgent funding needs, and meet customer demands for loans and provide convenience in seizing attractive and profitable investment opportunities.

Liquidity risk will occur when the bank is unable to provide cash flow for daily business operations or urgent funding needs. The size of this risk is determined by planning cash flow or fund flow, planning in managing the structure of funds, availability of assets and the ability to create access to the interbank market.

Broadly speaking, liquidity risk in bank operations occurs because:

- a. Banks have difficulty finding cash funds at a reasonable cost, either through loans or asset sales. Because interest on loans is prohibited, it is difficult for Islamic banks to obtain loans.
- b. The prohibition on selling debt securities other than the nominal value, has made it difficult for banks to find liquidity.

4. Operational Risk

Operational risk is the risk due to inadequate and/or non-functioning internal processes, human error, system failure and or external events that affect bank operations. In other words, operational risk is a risk that makes a bank unable to carry out its normal operational activities due to a natural disaster, fire, or other causes, for example, an intruder (hacker) who managed to infiltrate the bank's data center and disrupt the data. Broadly speaking, there are three factors that cause this risk, such as (1) Infrastructure, such as technology, policy, environment, security, disputes, and so on. (2) Process, and (3) Resources

This operational risk includes five things, namely:

- 1. Reputation risk**

Reputation risk is a risk caused by, among other things, negative publications related to bank activities or negative perceptions of the bank.

- 2. Compliance risk**

Compliance risk is the risk caused by non-compliance with existing regulations, both internal and external.

- 3. Transaction risk (transaction risk)**

Transaction risk is the risk caused by problems in the services or products provided.

- 4. Strategic risk (strategic risk)**

Strategic risk is the risk caused, among others, by the establishment and implementation of an inappropriate bank strategy, making inappropriate business decisions or the bank not complying with or not implementing changes to laws and other applicable provisions.

- 5. Legal risk (legal risk)**

Legal risk (legal risk) is the risk caused by the weakness of the juridical aspect, such as: the existence of lawsuits, the absence of supporting legislation or the weakness of the engagement (agreement) such as not fulfilling the conditions for the validity of an imperfect contract.

5 CONCLUSION

After doing research based on the process of research stages carried out, it can be concluded that risk disclosure is very important to be carried out in banking institutions. This is because banking institutions are very vulnerable to risk, with disclosure of the risks that will be faced by banking institutions in Indonesia in the future, a management can be carried out on these risks to minimize the adverse effects caused by these risks. Risk management is a science whose role is very important and should be applied in all fields of science. In essence, this risk management provides a systematic and structured view in solving problems that may arise in the future. The application of this risk management in the banking world is felt to be very necessary because the financial condition of a bank in a country greatly determines the financial condition of that country. This paper discusses the Basel Accord II convention which focuses more on risk management in a bank. With the use of risk management in the banking world, it is hoped that banks will become healthier so that the financial condition of a country will be better.

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